

USES OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION SYSTEM IN AN UNORGANIZED RETAIL SECTOR

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Abstract:

India's retail sector has gone through an evolution from the weekly fair, Kirana shops, to supermarkets. India has become the second-largest consumer market and seventh-largest retail market worldwide. Currently, it is flourishing and contributing to India's GDP and economic growth. Traditionally, the country's retail sector has been more of an unorganized type, however, with time, the western attitude slowly entered the country giving rise to organized retailing. The Use of Accounting Information System (AIS) in retail sector becomes an essential part in today's growing business. AIS provides an accounting and financial Information to decision makers of business that helps them to take corrective action at right time with right information. Since the trading of goods and services in the retail sector is on a regular basis, it is important to study and analyze the use of Accounting Information System (AIS) in Indian Retail Sector. This paper analyzes the accounting method used by the stores in an unorganised sector. The purpose of this study is to understand the challenges faced by this sector in adoption and using the accounting information system.

Key Words: *Accounting Information System (AIS), Retail Sector, Organised, Unorganised, Retailers.*

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Introduction

India's retail sector is considered to be one of the largest among all other sectors. Traditionally, retail sector in India were in the form of Haats, Mandis, and Melas. Retailing is basically the interaction between the producer and the consumer wherein the consumer buys products for final consumption. With the evolution of the Indian retail system over time, e-commerce has also made its way to enter this sector. As we look at

the statistics, the Indian retail sector is the 2nd largest global retail destination and is mostly dominated by the unorganized sector. It has been expected that around 220 million people will be shopping online by 2025. The industry is also expected to grow to US\$200 billion by the year 2027.

Typically, the sector in India has also witnessed a dynamic structure since many players have come into the market, and post-1991 and the LPG Model, the country has also attracted foreign companies and investors. While we look at the evolution of the retail sector, it first started with the emergence of Kirana stores and mom-and-pop stores. Bombay Dyeing, S Kumar's, Raymonds are a few of the examples of the first companies to come up with retail chains. Later, companies like Titan entered the organized retail sector.

A better picture of the retail sector is also shown by shopping malls in India. With technology, economic growth and competition, shopping malls emerged well and interpreted as an entertainment concept. Giving a world-class experience to the customers, shopping malls and cineplexes were built in the urban areas. Similarly, hypermarkets and supermarkets too emerged. Several factors contribute towards the evolution of the sector from the development in the supply chain management, distribution channels, technology to back-end operations.

Organized and Unorganized Retail Sector

The unorganized sector includes the units, the activity of which is not governed by any statute or legal provision, and they do not maintain any standard accounts. Products or services in an unorganized store could either be sold out at a fixed place or a mobile location, and the number of employees ranges between 10-20 people. Examples of an unorganized retail sector include the pan wala, cobbler, mom and pop stores, local sabzi mandi, general readymade garments shop or footwear shop, Kirana shop, mannered general stores, hand card, and pavement vendors. On the other hand, the organized sector includes the trading activities carried out by licensed retailers, those who are registered for sales, and other taxes. Examples of an organized retail sector include hypermarkets and retail chains, discount stores, drug stores, departmental stores, factory outlets, and large privately-owned retail businesses. These are professionally managed stores offering appealing goods and services, and a good ambiance that encourages customers to shop. Nike, Rebook, Big Bazaar, Raymonds, Sony, Apollo Pharmacy, Pizza Hut, Mcdonald's, etc are some examples of an organized retail store.

Accounting Information Systems in Retail

Accounting Information systems help retailers in planning, inventory control, managing budgets, and sales goals, and also helps in sale transactions and logistics. Retail accounting is important since it mitigates the risk of having human errors, and also saves time and money. A Software that has the combination of sales, purchasing, and inventory management helps in maintaining the records for the business. Along with this, the software that lets the retailer import transaction data, and easily create auditable records of purchases is much more convenient than any other traditional accounting method. Documenting assets and liabilities, expenses and revenues, and producing a real-time gross profit are the key factor of AIS.

Another important aspect of accounting in this sector is customer relationship management. CRM software is much more than having a phonebook, and this helps in analyzing and assessing customers' buying habits. A CRM platform with retail software will help in building marketing and sales strategies. Supply chain management is also one of the areas where a proper retail accounting solution is required in order to maintain warehouse management, returns, order management, etc. Apart from these, tracking inventory is important when there are multiple locations or even a big store. For this, having an accounting solution that tracks inventory will lead to an increase in profitability and also cut overhead costs. Point-of-Sale software has been in use at many big retail stores that provide customers with a smooth buying experience. The modern POS software features include payment processing, barcode scanning, special orders, returns, and end-of-day reporting.

Although, most of the Kirana stores currently use traditional ways of maintaining accounts wherein proper book-keeping is not maintained. It is mostly handwritten, and this is owing to the scope of that store cost, and time. Nowadays, with the advent of technology and the growth of the IT sector, even the unorganized retail stores have started with a computerized method of accounting with an aim to reduce any type of human errors, and also maintain records in an efficient manner.

Objectives

1. To analyze the use of Accounting Information System (AIS) in Indian Retail Sector.
2. To know the perception of retailers having unorganised retail shop on their use of AIS

Scope of Research

The present study aims at analyze the use of AIS in Indian Retail Sector. The Study covers

the perception of some retailers of unorganised retail sector regarding use of AIS in their day to day functioning of business and decision making. The study also aims to find out the challenges adopted by the sector in the use of AIS in their business activity.

Limitations of Research

The primary data collected for study is limited to the Ulhasnagar and Kalyan city only. Primary data may get biased and may influence by the behavior and mood of the respondents of whom survey is conducted.

Research Methodology

This study has a sample of Twenty Retailers having Unorganised retail shop from Ulhasnagar and Kalyan city, which is selected at convenience to know their perceptions on their use of AIS in their day to day business activity. Data has been collected using primary and secondary method of data collection. Primary data was collected through the structured questionnaire by Google forms to satisfy the objective of research paper and the secondary data was collected from various journals, articles, newspapers, magazines and websites. The collected data were further analyzed by using simple statistical tool like percentage.

Review of Literature:

Hajera Fatima Khan (September 2016): The Study on 'Accounting Information System: The Need of Modernisation' published in International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations ISSN 2348-7585. This Study provides an overview of the main objective of an accounting information system (AIS) and its uses, importance, and role in modernization of businesses. The results of the paper indicates that Accounting information systems plays an significant role in management decision making process by providing information to make proper and effective decision for the success and prosperity of the business in the modern world.

Hadi Saeidi, G.V. Bhavani Prasad, Hamid Saremi (October 2015): The Study on 'The Role of Accountants in Relation to Accounting Information Systems and Difference between Users of AIS and Users of Accounting.' Published in Bulletin Environmental Pharmacology Life Science, Vol 4 [11] ISSN115-123. This study helps in identifying the role of the accountants in the accounting information system and shows the difference between Users of AIS and users of accounting. The study also shows the roles that accountants has to play as far as accounting information system is concerned.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

A. Perspective of Unorganised Retailers on Use of AIS

I Profile of Respondents:

Types of Unorganized Retailer:

Unorganized Retail Shops are those that customers find it in their neighborhood or in a local area. These retail shops are found in different size in different form in local marketplace or besides the residential places. Thus, the respondents were asked about their form of retail outlet.

As shown in the above graph, majority of the respondents (30%) were having Kirana Store whereas 25% of the Respondents were having General Store. 26% of Respondents were having Garment Shops and 14% of Respondents are Service Provider.

Annual Turnover

These small retailers have knowingly or unknowingly implemented all management principles that we talk about in their business operations. They are a step ahead of most new organizations

– they are not only customer centric but are also able to earn profits.

The Annual Turnover is something which shows the requirements of Accounting required. As the Organised Retail Sector have huge turnover annually. It requires daily records of accounting data which means the AIS is used by Organised Retail Sector is on daily basis. Thus, it was important to know the annual turnover of retailers in Unorganised sector so as to know their requirements of maintaining accounting Information.

Here, as the Respondents were asked about their annual turnover at their preference. Which shows the 50% of respondents have annual income is between 11 to 20 lakh. Around 25% of respondents have annual income between 6 to 10 lakh. There are 15% of

Respondents who have annual income more than 20 lakhs and 10% of Respondents have less than 5 lakh.

The Annual Turnover of Unorganised Retail Sectors compare to Organised Retail Sector is less. It shows that these retailers can maintain books on monthly or annual basis.

Source: Data collected from survey

Ownership

Generally unorganized retailers consist of small retailers who carry business as Hindu Undivided Family business or sole proprietary basis or a partnership basis. Thus, respondents were asked about their business ownership type.

Source: Data collected from survey

Here, 65% of Respondents were having sole proprietorship and 35% of respondents were running business as Partnership or HUF. It shows Unorganised Retail businesses are mostly on sole proprietorship basis. That shows mostly unorganized retail sector is owned and managed by single person who is solely responsible for the profit /loss of the business.

Number of Employees

Requirements of Employees in Unorganised Retail Shop is very less or in most of the cases it is like one man show. Thus, Respondents were asked about the number of employees they hire in their business.

Source: Data collected from survey

Here, 60% of the respondents said that the number of employees hired by them are between 1 to 5. 25% of respondents said they have not hired any employee. 15% of respondents have hired more than 5 employees. From this we can say that the unorganized retailers in Ulhasnagar and Kalyan city does not require any accounting software relating to employees records

Maintaining Books of Accounts

In any form of business it is essential to maintain books of accounts. Thus, Respondents were asked whether they maintain books of accounts or not. 100% of Respondents agreed with the fact that they maintain books of accounts for recording their business transactions.

Respondents were also asked about the basis on which they maintain books of accounts whether on cash or accrual basis. Here, 65% of Retailers said they maintain books of accounts on Cash basis and 35% of retailers said they maintain books of accounts on Accrual basis.

Accounting of Unorganised Retail Sector

In Unorganised Retail Sector with their small scale of operations they either hired any accounting firm or an accountant or use software at their workplace or prefer manual recording of Accounting transaction. Thus, here the respondents were asked about their way of accounting of their business.

Source: Data collected from survey

Majority of the respondents (48%) does accounting of their business manually paper based on their own as their size of business is small. 38% of respondents hired accountant to maintain accounts of their business whereas only 14% of the respondents were using Accounting software by themselves at their workplace. It shows that still majority of the respondents do not use any of Accounting Information Software may be because of lack of capital or knowledge of accounting software or because of small scale operations.

Accounting Software

As the power of modern tools and technologies is prevailing in large companies, these retailers are finding it difficult to match and grow their business more than ever before. More retailers

are gradually realized that the difference in accounting methods and technology can bring to their business. These retailers are looking for Accounting Information Software and techniques which can help them to grow their business, and also help them with running it in a more efficient way. Thus, respondents were asked whether they use any of Accounting software or not.

Here, 35% of Respondents said ERP is the Accounting software they used for maintaining Accounting Information and preparing financial statements. Other Accounting software such as Quick Books and SAP both are used by 50% of respondents. There are around 15% of respondents who do not use any of the accounting software.

Source: Data collected from survey

Findings of the study:

Most of the retail business in Ulhasnagar and Kalyan city is driven by small traders, and mom and pop stores. There seems to be lack of awareness amongst the respondents regarding the importance and usage of accounting information system in the city of Ulhasnagar and Kalyan. The unorganized retailers are generally operating in small scale and hence they are happy with the traditional system. It was found that the retailers lack the required knowledge to operate the system. Also the AIS system calls for additional cost for the retailers for establishing the hardware and software for the implementation of the AIS as well as its maintenance cost. The retailers seem to be not ready to spend the huge expenditure considering the nature of their business.

Recommendation:

Owing to the consumer demands and evolving retail scenario, and on the basis of different studies, it is imperative for the unorganized retail stores to embrace digital technologies. These unorganized retail stores remain a source of living for many middle-income families, the growing organized retail sector could pose a threat to the unorganized retail stores when it comes to the volume of business, profits, accounts, and consequently, customer preference. The way ahead now is to adopt digital technologies, and utilize the modern method of accounting to widen the customer base, and compete with the organized retail sector. With digitization, creditworthiness will also increase, because the use of point-of-sale devices, digital payments, debit, and credit payments will generate data and help lenders extend credit. It is important to use the method of accounting that reduces risk, human errors, efforts and saves time. Keeping this in mind, a well-

structured accounting information system must be followed to make the operations efficient for both the owner as well as the customer.

Conclusion:

The retail sector has played a vital role throughout the world in increasing productivity of consumer goods and services. Accounting Information System (AIS) is now used at highest in Retail Sector. AIS use has become essential especially in Organized Retail Sector due to its gradually growing market segment and popularity in Indian Retail Sector.

There is large number of users of AIS in Organized Retail Sector who has multiple use of AIS. Whereas Unorganized retailer do not use AIS at their highest level as it is used only by limited retailers. There is a long way to go for the unorganized retailers to understand the system of Accounting information and for implementing the same in their business.

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